

Effect of treating single superphosphate with cowdung

B. Roy and J.N. Jha, Agricultural Research Institute, Mithapur, Patna, Bihar, India

We studied the effect of cowdung-treated single superphosphate (SSP) on panicles/m² and grain yield of rice variety Sita (135 d duration) in a 3-yr wet season field trial. Soil was dark gray, neutral heavy clay (pH 7.1) with poor drainage, medium fertility (0.75% organic C, 0.07% total N, 22 kg available P/ha, 185 kg available K/ha), and CEC 32.1 meq/ 100 g. P fertilizer was mixed with fresh cowdung in a 1:3 ratio 10-12 h before application. Six levels of P in addition to the P content of cowdung were used in a randomized block design with five replications.

Yields from treated plots were significantly higher than from control plots, indicative of nutrient deficiency in the soil (see table). P as SSP mixed with cowdung as a basal dose yielded significantly higher. P increased yields even when applied as late as at maximum tillering.

Both SSP alone and with cowdung applied basally and at maximum tillering increased panicles/m², except for SSP alone at tillering. □

Effect of cowdung-treated single superphosphate (SSP) on yield of grain and panicles of rice.^a Bihar, India, 1983-85.

Treatment ^b	Mean grain yield (t/ha)	Mean panicles/m ²
Control (no P)	2.94 c	252 b
17.2 kg P as SSP, basal	3.43 b	270 a
17.2 kg P as SSP, 20 DT	3.35 b	249 b
17.2 kg P as SSP + cowdung (1:3), basal	3.93 a	277 a
17.2 kg P as SSP + cowdung (1:3), 20 DT	3.60 ab	274 a

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level.

^bDT = days after transplanting.

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Sources and methods of N application for irrigated wetland rice

M.R. Patel and N.D. Desai, Main Rice Research Station (MRRS), Nawagam, India

We studied sources and methods of N application for irrigated wetland rice on a sandy loam soil with pH 7.0, organic matter 0.9%, total N 0.07%, and CEC 12.2 meq/ 100 g. The test variety was GR-11.

Prilled urea (PU) local best split and standard best split, sulfur-coated urea (SCU), urea supergranules (USG), and Massoorie-phosphorus-coated urea (MPCU) at 58, 87, and 116 kg N/ ha were compared. (MPCU is an indigenous material supplied by Madras Fertilizer Limited.)

In the local best split application, PU (46% N) was applied in 4 equal

splits: basal, at maximum tillering, panicle initiation, and booting stage. In standard best split application, PU was applied 2/3 basal and 1/3 topdressed 5 to 7 d before panicle initiation, incorporated with no standing water. SCU (36% N) was incorporated 6 d after transplanting (DT). USG (46% N) was placed in the center of every 4 hills at 10-12 cm soil depth 6 DT. MPCU (32% N) was basally applied and incorporated before transplanting.

Treatment significantly affected panicles/m² (see table). At 87 kg N/ha, USG gave significantly more panicles than SCU.

USG at 58 kg N/ ha yielded significantly higher than MPCU and urea best split. SCU at 87 and 116 kg N/ ha produced significantly higher yields than all treatments except USG. □

Grain yield and panicles/m² with different N sources and application methods, Nawagam, India.

Treatment (kg N/ha)	Form and application method	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles/m ² (no.)
0	No N	2.16	163
58	PU best split (local)	3.31	203
58	PU standard best split	2.68	210
58	SCU broadcast and incorporated	3.69	280
58	USG placed 10-12 cm deep	4.34	308
58	MPCU broadcast and incorporated	2.91	236
87	PU best split (local)	3.56	249
87	PU standard best split	3.34	247
87	SCU broadcast and incorporated	4.88	289
87	USG placed 10-12 cm deep	4.44	341
87	MPCU broadcast and incorporated	3.70	294
116	PU best split (local)	3.95	277
116	PU standard best split	3.31	273
116	SCU broadcast and incorporated	4.96	296
116	USG placed 10-12 cm deep	4.52	303
116	MPCU broadcast and incorporated	3.90	280
	CD (0.05)	0.76	41

Performance of Azospirillum biofertilizer in irrigated and rainfed upland rice

A. Balasubramanian and K. Kumar, Agricultural Microbiology Department, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Madurai 625104, India

We studied the field performance of a local isolate of *Azospirillum lipoferum*

under irrigated and rainfed upland conditions.

The irrigated experiment was laid out with IR50 rice in a red sandy loam soil (pH 7.6, EC 0.35 mmho, 265 kg N, 12.2 kg P, 276 kg K/ha). Different levels of fertilizer N with and without *Azospirillum* biofertilizer were compared.

Sixty kg seed/ ha were uniformly coated with 1 kg *Azospirillum*

inoculant which contained approximately 10^8 cells/g of peat soil carrier, following the recommended seed treatment method. After sprouting, the soaked seeds were sown in the nursery bed and 2 kg *Azospirillum* biofertilizer mixed with 25 kg powdered farmyard manure (FYM) was broadcast. In the main field, 2 kg *Azospirillum* biofertilizer mixed with 25 kg of powdered FYM/ha was broadcast before transplanting. The roots of 25-d-old rice seedlings were dipped in a water-slurry of 1 kg *Azospirillum* for 20 min before transplanting in 16-m² plots in a randomized block design with 3 replications. Tillers and dry weight were recorded 60 d after transplanting, and grain and straw yields at harvest.

Tillering was enhanced by increased fertilizer N (Table 1) and *Azospirillum* biofertilizer significantly increased tiller numbers and plant dry weight at all fertilizer levels. Maximum increase in plant dry weight was with 50% fertilizer N.

Azospirillum biofertilizer treatment markedly increased the grain and straw yields at all N levels (Table 2). Grain yield response to *Azospirillum* biofertilizer was more pronounced at lower levels of fertilizer N (0 and 50%). Significant increases in tiller numbers, plant dry weight, and grain yield also were obtained at 100% N level with *Azospirillum* treatment, indicating that the higher level of fertilizer N (75 kg N/ha) did not inhibit activity of the *Azospirillum* strain. The mean grain yield at 50% N fertilizer level with *Azospirillum* treatment equaled yield with 100% N fertilizer alone.

Effect of combining chemical N and *Sesbania aculeata* in upland rice

N. Hati, Agronomy Department, College of Agriculture, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Bhubaneswar 751003 Orissa, India

The lateritic sandy-loam upland soils of Bhubaneswar are low in organic

Table 1. Effect of *Azospirillum* biofertilizer on tillering and dry weight of irrigated IR50 at Madurai, India.^a

Fertilizer level	Tillers/plant (no.)		Dry wt (g/plant)	
	No <i>Azospirillum</i>	<i>Azospirillum</i> inoculant at 6 kg/ha	No <i>Azospirillum</i>	<i>Azospirillum</i> inoculant
No N	12.0	15.0	10.3	11.8
50% N	14.7	16.1	11.0	13.9
15% N	15.3	19.0	13.2	14.9
100% N	11.3	20.1	14.5	15.5
CD (P = 0.05%)	1.6	1.6	0.03	0.03

^a Means of 9 observations.

Table 2. Influence of *Azospirillum* biofertilizer on grain and straw yields of irrigated and rainfed upland rice, Madurai, India.

Fertilizer level	Grain yield (t/ha)		Increase (%)	Straw yield (t/ha)		Increase (%)
	Untreated	<i>Azospirillum</i> inoculated		Untreated	<i>Azospirillum</i> inoculated	
<i>Irrigated (IR50)</i>						
No N	2.1	3.2	47.1	5.6	5.8	3.6
50% N	3.3	4.1	24.5	6.6	7.7	20.6
15% N	3.2	4.4	17.6	7.1	8.3	16.1
100% N	4.2	5.2	22.7	8.7	9.8	2.6
CD (P = 0.05)	0.2	0.2		0.156	0.156	
<i>Rainfed upland (PMK. 1)</i>						
No N	2.0	2.2	15.4	2.5	3.4	43.4
50% N	2.3	2.9	25.9	3.6	4.6	21.4
75% N	2.4	2.9	18.0	4.0	4.8	20.4
100% N	2.9	3.1	6.0	4.9	5.8	18.8
CD (P = 0.05%)	0.04	0.04		0.1	0.1	

The rainfed upland experiment was in a rainfed banded field at Paramakudi. With rice starch solution as adhesive, seeds of PMK. 1 were coated with *Azospirillum* biofertilizer at 1 kg peat-based inoculant/75 kg seeds per ha. In addition, 2 kg biofertilizer/ha was mixed with 15 kg dry powdered FYM and broadcast in the main field before direct seeding. Three levels of fertilizer N in the form

of urea were applied.

Maximum increase in grain yield due to *Azospirillum* biofertilizer treatment was with the 50% N level (20 kg N/ha) (Table 2). Grain yield at this level equaled that with full fertilizer N, *Azospirillum* biofertilizer enhanced straw yield at all N levels; the maximum increase was at zero-N level. □

matter (0.43 to 0.5% C), base status (CEC 3.8-4.1 meq/100 g soil), pH (5.1 to 5.4), and available P (14 kg/ha, Bray's) and high in Fe and Al. But farmers rarely use farmyard manure or compost because the manures are diverted to produce rice in low and medium lands. Moreover, farmers hesitate to grow a green manure crop in lieu of a kharif crop.

During 1985-86 kharif, upland rice

Subhadra was sown at 100 kg/ha in 15- × 10-cm rows with and without *Sesbania aculeata* broadcast at 40 kg seed/ha with 4 N levels. Half the N was applied at sowing, half at tillering. All treatments received a basal 13 kg P and 25 kg K/ha.

At 20 d after germination, sesbania plants were killed by spraying 0.9% propanil. The leaves and the stems created a temporary mulch that